

Ecocide as a Threat to Global Security: Exploring the Recognition of Ecocide as an International Crime and its Implications

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Abstract

As environmental degradation continues to worsen, the idea of ecocide is gaining attention as a major global security concern. This paper argues that ecocide, defined as severe, widespread, or long-term damage to the environment, presents a significant threat to global stability and should be recognized as an international crime. The paper explores the history of discussions around ecocide, tracing its connections to the concept of genocide and earlier attempts to criminalize environmental destruction in international law. It then examines current efforts to incorporate ecocide into international law, focusing on the proposal to add it as a fifth crime to the Rome Statute. While acknowledging the potential benefits of this step, the paper also critically evaluates the challenges involved, including the International Criminal Court's limited membership and the difficulties in agreeing on a universal definition. By looking at examples such as the Vietnam War, the draining of the Mesopotamian Marshes, and the destruction of the Nova Kakhovka dam, this analysis shows how ecocide contributes to humanitarian crises, resource scarcity, and regional instability. The paper concludes that recognizing ecocide as an international crime, whether through amending the Rome Statute or establishing a specialized environmental court, is crucial for deterring widespread environmental destruction and promoting global environmental justice, though achieving this requires significant international cooperation, especially from major global powers.

Keywords: Ecocide, International Criminal Court (ICC), International Law, Global Security,

Introduction

In an era of escalating environmental degradation and geopolitical instability, the concept of "ecocide" is gaining increased interest as a pressing global issue requiring urgent regulation and possible recognition as an international crime. Ecocide, defined by the Independent Expert Panel as "*unlawful or wanton acts committed with knowledge that there is a substantial likelihood of severe and either widespread or long-term damage to the environment being caused by those acts,*" (Stop Ecocide International, 2021, Article 8 ter) has been discussed primarily in terms of its environmental impact. However, its broader implications for global security and geopolitics must be further explored.

This paper argues that ecocide poses a significant threat to global security and should therefore be defined and recognized in international law. This paper will analyze various ways to achieve this and the potential implications for international security. One possibility that is believed to have gained the most support is recognizing ecocide as an international crime by adding it to the list of crimes that can be prosecuted by the International Criminal Court (ICC). However, the possible benefits and drawbacks of this strategy will also be examined, considering the difficulties posed by the fact that two of the world's most powerful nations—China and the United States—are neither parties to the Rome Statute nor recognize the International Criminal Court. Even though adding ecocide to the Rome Statute might be a big step, more international cooperation and commitment are needed for it to be effective.

1. History of the Term "Ecocide"

The term "ecocide" was first introduced in the

early 1970s by Yale botanist Arthur Galston, who described the environmental destruction caused by the US military's use of herbicidal chemicals during the Vietnam War (Bertram, 2024). As part of Operation Hades, between 1961 and 1971, the US Army sprayed over 73 million liters of chemical agents on Vietnamese territory in an attempt to eliminate the vegetation that provided cover for Viet Cong forces in "enemy territory." The military also deliberately targeted crops with a range of defoliants. The poisonous spray, known as Agent Orange, contained the hazardous substance dioxin in approximately 45 million liters, leading to a slow-moving disaster in Vietnam with serious long-term effects on the country's ecology, economy, and health (von Meding, 2017).

However, discussions about environmental crimes began long before the Vietnam War. Etymologically, the term ecocide is linked to genocide, which was introduced in the 1930s by Raphael Lemkin, a Polish Jewish lawyer, and included in the 1948 UN Genocide Convention (hereby referred to as "the Convention") (Nowak, 2023). Lemkin's concept of genocide included two forms: physical genocide, committed by killing individuals, and cultural genocide, committed by undermining the way of life of a particular group (Nowak, 2023). His definition identified the destruction of a people by factors not directly involved in killing (Higgins et al., 2012). According to Lemkin, acts of genocide return humanity to the dark ages, shock the conscience of humanity and raise serious concerns about the future of civilization (Nowak, 2023).

Therefore, the concept of ecocide is based on the same principle as genocide. It can result in cultural damage and destruction. Like genocide, ecocide can be direct or indirect; it can involve the destruction of a territory or the undermining of a way of life—both environmental and cultural (Higgins et al., 2012). Lemkin saw the destruction of culture

as an important form of group destruction. For him, culture is part of the collective memory, and the destruction of a particular group's culture leads directly to the destruction of that group. He viewed national cultures as important elements of world culture. Thus, the destruction of a group is the destruction of part of the culture of humanity (Higgins et al., 2012). According to Lemkin, it is the shared culture of a social group that gives rise to the *genos* in acts of genocide. Lemkin claimed that "cultural genocide is the most important part of the Convention," although cultural genocide was ultimately not included in the legal definition of genocide (Higgins et al., 2012, p. 8).

According to Galligan (2021), cultural genocide described by Lemkin, is key to the ecocide-genocide connection. Lemkin emphasized that "culture integrates human societies" and is "necessary for realizing material needs," (Galligan, 2021, p. 1007) which means that destroying a group's culture, including its connection to the environment, can be genocidal. Therefore, ecocide can be seen as a form of cultural destruction.

During reviews of the Convention's effectiveness, the first attempts were made to criminalize environmental destruction under international law (Higgins et al., 2012). In this context, Richard A. Falk prepared the draft of the International Convention on the Crime of Ecocide, which was included in a study by the UN Sub-Commission on Prevention of Discrimination and Protection of Minorities. He described the US war in Indochina as the first modern instance where the environment was deliberately targeted for systematic destruction in war (Falk, 1973).

Moreover, Falk (1973) linked ecocide and genocide, stating that "Just as counterinsurgency warfare tends toward genocide with respect to the people, so it tends toward ecocide with respect to the environment" (Falk, 1973, p. 80). He also notices the need to acknowledge that "man has intentionally and unintentionally inflicted irreparable damage to the environment

in times of war and peace" and that "we are living in a period of increasing danger of ecological collapse" (Higgins et al., 2012, p. 9). Moreover, he emphasized that most victims of environmental crime are Global South nations, which reinforces global inequalities and shows that environmental protection should be a human rights issue (Falk, 1973).

Falk's proposal of the Ecocide Convention mainly addresses ecocide as a deliberate war crime and does not specify provisions during peacetime. By this time, a majority of UN Member States supported ecocide as a crime during peacetime. However, the draft International Convention on the Crime of Ecocide was shelved for unknown reasons (Higgins et al., 2012).

Between 1984 and 1996, the International Law Commission (ILC) considered including environmental damage and ecocide in the list of Crimes Against Peace. However, in 1996, at a meeting of the ILC, Chairman Ahmed Mahiou decided to remove ecocide as a separate provision. The final article adopted by the ILC and amended by the Drafting Committee refers to intentionally causing "widespread, long-term, and severe damage to the natural environment" within a war context (Higgins et al., 2012, p. 3). This was the last reference to a crime against the environment that made it into the Rome Statute (Higgins et al., 2012). Speculations exist about why the provision criminalizing ecocide was not included. For example, Higgins quotes Christian Tomuschat, a long-term ILC member, who suggested that:

[One] cannot escape the impression that nuclear arms played a decisive role in the minds of many of those who opted for the final text which now has been emasculated to such an extent that its conditions of applicability will almost never be met even after humankind would have gone through disasters of the most atrocious kind as a consequence of conscious action by

persons who were completely aware of the fatal consequences their decisions would entail. (Higgins et al., 2012, p. 3)

2. Current Approaches to Integrating Ecocide into International Law

After the Rome Statute failed to include it as a stand-alone provision, ecocide has been largely ignored in policy discussions for the past few decades. However, in recent years, it has regained attention due to the intensifying climate crisis, the rise of environmental justice movements, and increasing recognition of environmental destruction as a threat to peace and human rights (van den Heede, 2023). Interest significantly increased in 2010, when Scottish lawyer Polly Higgins proposed that ecocide be considered the "fifth international crime against peace," and a transnational civil society campaign to enshrine ecocide in national and international law was initiated by Higgins' proposal (Bertram, 2024, para. 4). Higgins defined ecocide as "the extensive damage to, destruction of or loss of ecosystem(s) of a given territory, whether by human agency or by other causes to such an extent that peaceful enjoyment by the inhabitants of that territory has been severely diminished" (van den Heede, 2023, p. 435).

In 2021, the Independent Expert Panel for the Legal Definition of Ecocide (IEP), established by the Stop Ecocide International Foundation, developed a new definition of ecocide with the objective of establishing a definition that could serve as the basis for an amendment to the Rome Statute, that would add ecocide to the list of the international crimes next to genocide, war crimes, crimes against humanity and crimes of aggression (van den Heede, 2023). The Panel defined ecocide as "unlawful or wanton acts committed with knowledge of likely severe, widespread, or long-term environmental damage" (*Stop Ecocide International*, 2021, Article 8 ter).

While the definition was in general positively received, as it emphasizes the need for

international legal frameworks to address the serious environmental damage that can happen in times of both peace and war, as well as the purpose behind environmental damage, connecting it to intentional acts that may have far-reaching and protracted effects, it also sparked some criticism in the literature (Heller, 2021). For example, Heller notices that the concept of genocide, on which ecocide is based, is legally defined as acts committed with the intent to destroy, in whole or in part, a national, ethnical, racial or religious group. This specific targeting is a core element of genocide. Ecocide, on the other hand, focuses on the destruction of the environment, which may not always be aimed at harming a particular group. Therefore, the broad nature of environmental damage makes it difficult to classify under the narrowly defined scope of ecocide, leading to challenges in legal interpretation and enforcement. In addition, proving the specific intent behind ecocide can be difficult, as environmental damage, according to the IEP definition, may result from negligence or reckless acts rather than a deliberate intent to destroy a group, as it is a case for genocide (Heller, 2021).

Therefore, Heller proposes an alternative approach to defining ecocide that does not rely on the framework of genocide. Heller suggests focusing on the environmental damage itself and argues for a clear, stand-alone legal definition that treats serious environmental damage as an international crime. This approach aims to avoid the complications arising from the link between genocide and ecocide and to ensure that ecocide is recognized and prosecuted on its own merits, reflecting the urgent need to protect the environment from widespread and intentional damage (Heller, 2021).

2.1 Proposal to Include Ecocide in the Rome Statute

In February 2024, the Office of the Prosecutor launched a public consultation on a new policy

initiative to advance accountability for environmental crimes under the Rome Statute, and the prosecutor Khan stated: "Damage to the environment poses an existential threat to all life on the planet" (The Office of the Prosecutor, 2024).

The discussion on including the ecocide as the fifth crime intensified when Vanuatu, Fiji, and Samoa proposed amendment to the Rome Statute to include a Crime of Ecocide in September 2024, defining ecocide as "unlawful or wanton acts committed with knowledge that there is a substantial likelihood of severe and either widespread or long-term damage to the environment being caused by those acts," using the Independent Expert Panel definition from 2021 (Eco Jurisprudence Monitor, 2024). The main reason to come up with this proposal was that "a crime to protect the environment in peacetime as well as conflict is of fundamental importance, not only to cover the inadequacies of existing law, but also to promote a shift in mindset in both contexts to reflect an understanding of the severity of the danger posed by grave environmental harms" (Permanent Mission of the Republic of Vanuatu to the UN, 2024).

Vanuatu's Special Envoy on Climate Change and the Environment, Ralph Regenvanu, emphasized during the Session of the Assembly of States Parties to the Rome Statute in December 2024 that to protect the environment and human rights, enforceable standards and international cooperation are needed. He stressed that "to adequately protect the environment, upon which all human rights ultimately depend, enforceable standards are required, as well as meaningful international cooperation through domestic, regional and international spheres. The Rome Statute, as well as the fora provided by the International Criminal Court more generally, offer legitimate tools for ensuring effective collective action in this regard" (Regenvanu, 2024).

Vanuatu's initiative is a key example of growing support towards recognizing ecocide as a

crime. According to Root, including ecocide in the Rome Statute would provide a powerful legal tool to hold individuals and corporations accountable for severe environmental harm, particularly when they act with reckless disregard for the consequences. Once added to the Rome Statute, ecocide could be prosecuted in any ratifying jurisdiction where there's a connection to the case, expanding the scope of enforceability globally (Root, 2024).

However, this proposal might face numerous challenges. Amending the Rome Statute to incorporate ecocide necessitates a two-thirds majority vote among the Assembly of States Parties, which comprises 125 Member States (ICC, 2024). This high threshold means that gaining sufficient support is a difficult task, particularly given the varying national interests and priorities. Some countries, including major powers such as the United States, China, and India, are not parties to the Rome Statute, which further complicates efforts to achieve universal support for the amendment (Andrade, 2024). Therefore, Andrade (2024) claims that criminalizing ecocide at the international level presents challenges that could potentially weaken the system of international law. The non-universal membership of the International Criminal Court (ICC), with key countries like the U.S., China, and Russia not being signatories, means that even successful adoption of an ecocide amendment would lack global support. Furthermore, defining ecocide is a complex task, with disagreements over what constitutes mass environmental harm, leading to the risk of diluting the definition for broader acceptance. Therefore, according to Andrade (2024), this could fragment the international legal system, undermining its credibility and effectiveness in addressing environmental destruction.

3. National Regulations on Ecocide

This definition, proposed by the Independent Expert Panel, sparked discussions and in many

cases led to the introduction of ecocide legislation in various parliaments around the world, particularly in the EU, where an increasing number of states have included "ecocide" in their criminal codes. For example, in August 2021, France codified ecocide, followed by Belgium, which adopted a comprehensive ecocide law based on the IEP definition, marking a significant development in Western legal systems (Bertram, 2024). The criminalization of serious, widespread and long-term environmental damage is a notable legislative achievement of the Belgian ecocide law, which is set out in Article 94 of the new Criminal Code. The Belgian law imposes a higher mens rea threshold for *dolus indirectus*, requiring knowledge of severe, widespread and long-term damage, as opposed to the Independent Expert Panel's definition, which only requires knowledge of a substantial likelihood of damage. It is difficult to prosecute under this strict requirement. Furthermore, the law's applicability is limited to violations of binding international instruments or federal legislation, which may exclude many regional environmental protections and reduce its effectiveness (Bertram, 2024).

In addition to individual countries, the debate about criminalizing eco-violence is also taking place within the European Union, where the revised Environmental Crime Directive (ECD), approved by the EU Parliament and Council in November 2023, marks one of the latest developments. The ECD, which was passed by the Parliament in February 2024 and entered into force on 20 May 2024 (European Commission, 2024), makes several prohibited behaviors illegal and increases the severity of penalties for acts that result in "widespread and substantial damage that is either irreversible or long-lasting" (Bertram, 2024, para. 30). This directive lowers the mens rea threshold to facilitate prosecution by adopting a cumulative threshold of "serious, widespread and long-term damage" similar to Belgian law (Bertram, 2024, para. 30). It also includes a more lenient definition of unlawfulness and specifies serious negligence for certain conduct. The push for a new international

environmental crime will be aided by the requirement that EU Member States update their environmental criminal laws if the proposal is adopted (Bertram, 2024).

Adopted on 26 March 2024 and published on 30 April 2024, the EU became the first international body to successfully incorporate the idea of ecocide, rather than the term itself, into its new Directive on the Protection of the Environment through Criminal Law. The directive sets out minimum requirements and penalties for a range of environmental offenses. Although not classified as “ecocide,” certain offenses may be considered “qualified offenses” if they are intentional and cause extensive and long-lasting damage to ecosystems, habitats, or the quality of air, soil, or water. The preamble to the Directive suggests that this could include acts that are similar to ‘ecocide’ (Colin et al, 2024).

While, as described, many states are discussing the criminalization of ecocide in their penal codes, some have recognized ecocide for decades, but enforcement in these countries has been weak (Bertram, 2024). Vietnam, for example, was the first country to incorporate the crime of ecocide into its domestic law, having been the first to experience ecocide during the Vietnam War. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, many newly formed states included ecocide as a named crime against peace in their criminal codes, including Armenia, Belarus, the Republic of Moldova, Ukraine and Georgia (Higgins et al., 2012). It is important to stress that these states included ecocide in their criminal codes under the influence of the Draft Code of Crimes against the Peace and Security of Mankind, when ecocide was first proposed for international adoption and named as a crime against the peace and security of mankind, which was discussed in the previous chapters (Higgins et al., 2012). However, all these legislative efforts to codify ecocide show its importance in maintaining global peace and security.

Examining how the regulations look in China is also insightful because China is one of the major polluters and plays an important role in global environmental governance. Currently, the concept of “ecocide” is not recognized in law and has not been mentioned in any recent legislative proposals. However, China has environmental protection laws and environmental crimes. Traditional air and water pollution, illegal waste disposal and illegal poaching of endangered animals are just a few examples of these offenses (Colin et al, 2024). However, China is formally pursuing a “green” transformation, incorporating ecological initiatives into its political strategy in response to the severe ecological degradation the country faces, symbolized by widespread smog and natural disasters (Clement, 2021).

4. Ecocide and International Security: Global Examples and Implications

Ecocide has significant implications for international security. However, due to the lack of a universally agreed-upon definition, the term is used in literature not as a legal term but as a descriptor for extensive damage and destruction of ecosystems. Examining examples from different regions helps to understand how ecocide poses a threat to international security. The Vietnam War is a key example, as it sparked increased international discussion about ecocide. The US military's use of herbicidal warfare during the Vietnam War— specifically, Operation Ranch Hand—devastated the environment and had a significant impact on international security (Zierler, 2011). Herbicide use resulted in widespread ecological destruction, contaminated soil and water, long-term health issues, and community displacements, in addition to its goal of destroying crops and forests to deny the Viet Cong food.

Degradation of the environment affected local economies, increased social tensions, and threatened regional stability, which has an effect on international security (Zierler, 2011). The situation involving the Marsh Arabs in Iraq is another noteworthy instance that is regarded

as ecocide in the literature (Zierler, 2011). To punish the Marsh Arabs after the Gulf War, Saddam Hussein's regime purposefully drained the Mesopotamian Marshes, which resulted in thousands of people being uprooted and the destruction of a distinctive cultural legacy. This act of environmental warfare fueled insurgencies and sectarian tensions while also exacerbating regional instability and creating a humanitarian crisis. The world community mobilized efforts to restore the marshes and resettle displaced populations after recognizing this act as ecocide.

Another instance of ecocide is thought to have occurred in Iraq between 2014 and 2017, when Daesh destroyed natural resources and set fire to oil wells, among other environmental atrocities (Abad Castelos, 2023). These activities contributed to resource scarcity, community displacement, increased competition and conflict, and long-term ecological impacts, in addition to widespread environmental degradation and health risks. The depletion of natural resources significantly threatened regional and global security and damaged local economies and peace initiatives.

The examples described took place during a military conflict as acts of environmental warfare. However, there are also examples in the literature that suggest that ecocide can also occur in peacetime. For example, Mwangi (2007) describes the Lesotho Highlands Water Project as an ecocide. The project was initiated in the 1980s as a joint venture between Lesotho and South Africa, with serious environmental and social consequences. The author claims that it led to the loss of arable land, increased soil erosion and destroyed the habitats of numerous species, displacing thousands of households and causing economic hardship and social instability. The depletion of community resources and long-term environmental degradation exacerbated these problems. A very different example is

described by Walters (2022). The author argues that the bushfires that occurred in Australia in 2019 and 2020 can also be described as ecocide because the government's failure to act on expert advice and climate warnings can be seen as gross negligence, which contributed significantly to the scale of the disaster. The bushfires caused unprecedented damage, including loss of life, destruction of homes and massive environmental degradation (Walters, 2022). However, this example raises the question of whether these bushfires constitute ecocide and highlights the need for legal frameworks to hold political leaders accountable for environmental destruction.

Another case documented in academic works is the plight of Nauru, a tiny Pacific island nation that has experienced extreme environmental degradation as a result of extensive phosphate mining and climate change. The author refers to this phenomenon as ecocide (Kanngieser, 2020). Soil erosion, water pollution and loss of biodiversity caused by mining have created unfavorable living conditions. Displacement, inadequate access to food and water, and poor health are the results of these environmental stresses. Potential migration from Nauru due to climate change poses a threat to regional stability and illustrates the convergence of geopolitical strategy and natural disasters.

China has also been accused of ecocide. The country's construction of dams on the Mekong River has caused serious environmental damage, resulting in crop failures and humanitarian emergencies in downstream countries (Quang & Borton, 2020). The problem is exacerbated by the lack of legally binding frameworks for cooperation, leading to serious ecological damage and international disputes over water resources. In addition, the creation of artificial islands in the South China Sea poses a serious risk to marine ecosystems, possibly even leading to ecocide. Construction and dredging activities may result in centuries-old coral reefs being covered in sediment, jeopardizing ecosystems that are essential for the preservation of fish stocks in

the area (Langenheim, 2015). Environmental damage might exacerbate territorial disputes and geopolitical tensions.

The most recent ecocide discussed in the literature, occurring again during a war, is the destruction of the Nova Kakhovka dam in Ukraine in June 2023, when Russia was accused that its actions unleashed a catastrophic flood resulting in the immediate deaths of 50 people and the displacement of tens of thousands of civilians (Kostin, 2024). Vital resources, including drinking water reservoirs for over a million people and hundreds of thousands of hectares of farmland, were contaminated, and dangerous substances such as landmines, industrial chemicals and 150 tonnes of industrial lubricants polluted the Dnipro River, causing severe long-term ecological damage (Kostin, 2024). Moreover, the spill caused unprecedented damage to critical habitats, including those listed under the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands of International Importance, such as the UNESCO Black Sea Biosphere Reserve (Kostin, 2024).

Since Russia denied its involvement, several criminal proceedings were initiated. As of April 2025, investigations into the destruction of the Kakhovka Dam are being conducted by the International Criminal Court and the Ukrainian Prosecutor General's Office, focusing on potential charges of war crimes, environmental crimes, and crimes against humanity (Hansen, 2023). While Ukraine has identified a Russian general as a suspect (Formusek, 2024) the investigations face challenges due to the ongoing conflict and limited access to the dam site, which is under Russian control. The UN Commission of Inquiry on Ukraine is also investigating the incident and its impact on the civilian population (UNHCR, 2023). However, while accountability for perpetrators might be difficult to achieve, the ongoing investigations show the importance of strong regulations of environmental crime.

In conclusion, these cases—occurring in times of both peace and conflict—highlight the urgent need for an internationally recognized definition of ecocide to hold perpetrators accountable. The reported environmental damage draws attention to important security implications, such as humanitarian emergencies and displacement. Displacement caused by environmental degradation often leads to refugee crises, putting pressure on humanitarian aid and international relations. Another effect of environmental degradation is regional instability, as it can increase tensions, fuel conflicts and threaten stability. Lack of resources increases rivalry and hostilities over the few remaining resources and impacts livelihoods and health, causing social unrest and economic hardship. The combination of geopolitical maneuvering and environmental disasters shows us that there is a need to manage resources more fairly and work together internationally. Moreover, referring to Lemkin's view that genocide is inherently colonial (Galligan, 2021) ecocide is also very often a result of colonial and extractivist practices, which devastate already vulnerable communities, as the described examples have shown. Ecocide could be seen as a systematic outcome of colonial domination and not only isolated environmental harm (Galligan, 2021). Therefore, recognizing ecocide as an international crime could not only contribute to international security but also acknowledge its historical injustice to achieve a more sustainable global order.

5. Discussion

The examples described in the previous chapter underscore the urgent need for a clear, internationally recognized definition of ecocide that applies in both wartime and peacetime. As Kostin (2024) notes, without a universal standard, perpetrators of serious environmental damage can evade justice by exploiting inconsistencies between national legal systems, while the prospect of international prosecution can act as a powerful deterrent. Currently, some aspects of environmental crimes are included in the Rome Statute, but these provisions are

limited to wartime and do not specifically address ecocide. Article 8(2)(b)(iv) of the Rome Statute and Article 35(3) of the First Additional Protocol to the Geneva Conventions of 1977 were pioneering in establishing a framework for recognizing ecocide as a war crime, criminalizing intentional attacks that cause excessive environmental damage relative to the military advantage gained (Bray, 2023). However, this provision has never been used by the International Criminal Court.

However, the destruction of the Nova Kakhovka dam has reignited the debate on environmental crimes, suggesting that the ICC may need to prove its ability to deal with such crimes. This event has been described as “ecocide” by various parties, including the Ukrainian government. The ICC has launched an investigation into this event, which could potentially mark its first investigation into environmental crimes, representing a significant step forward for international criminal justice (Hansen, 2023).

At the same time, as noted above, there is a proposal for a definition of ecocide prepared by the IEP, which argues for its inclusion as a fifth, independent crime, even in peacetime, in the Rome Statute, to be prosecuted by the ICC. However, there is an ongoing debate about whether the ICC is the most appropriate institution to investigate ecocide. Hosa (2023) argues that criminalizing environmental damage at the international level is complex, noting that proving intent in environmental crimes is challenging. The ICC has also been criticized for its limited jurisdiction, as major global powers such as the US, China, and Russia are not parties to the Rome Statute, and its trials could potentially prolong conflicts. In addition, the ICC has been accused of bias, particularly against African nations, and of lacking the political will to prosecute crimes committed by Western powers (Faizi, 2021). Its limited geographical jurisdiction further limits its effectiveness. Of the 193 UN Member

States, only 125 have ratified the Rome Statute (ICC, 2024). Another important weakness of the ICC is that it lacks its own enforcement mechanism, which means that state parties have to be willing to cooperate with the Court.

Furthermore, since the ICC has typically handled a small number of cases, adding ecocide to its mandate could lessen its effectiveness due to capacity and financial limitations (Van Den Heede, 2023). ICC judges are primarily experts in criminal law, not environmental law. They will mainly rely on outside experts to interpret scientific evidence because they lack experience with environmental matters; this could complicate proceedings and result in misunderstandings or misinterpretations (Van Den Heede, 2023).

To address these issues, some authors suggest establishing alternative institutions such as an International Environmental Court, proposed by Murphy (2000). According to the author, this court, set up through a new international treaty, could have broad jurisdiction and apply international environmental law to various disputes, including transnational environmental damage, international environmental treaties, and ecocide (Murphy, 2000). Another proposal advocates establishing an International Court for the Environment attached to the International Court of Justice. This court would handle disputes involving state and non-state actors, issue emergency measures, mediate conflicts, and enforce global environmental treaties. Such an institution could address the pressing challenges of climate change and environmental degradation on a global scale, filling the gaps in existing international legal frameworks (Hockmann, 2009; Merz et al., 2014).

The last proposal worth mentioning is an Environmental Security Council, proposed by Faizi (2021). The author advocates the creation of an Environmental Security Council as an independent multilateral body under the UN to address the growing number of environmental crimes. According to Faizi, the ESC would have

judicial powers to prosecute ecocide and policy-making powers for global environmental management. It would consist of a judicial wing, modeled on the International Criminal Court, and a technical/policy wing, in which all willing UN Member States would participate on a “one country, one vote” basis. The ESC could draw its legal basis from existing instruments such as the Convention on Biological Diversity and would be created by a treaty negotiated in the UN General Assembly (Faizi, 2021).

In conclusion, recognizing ecocide as an international crime is necessary to tackle current global challenges, but it requires political will as well as a thorough legal framework. To deter environmental crimes and promote global environmental justice, ecocide must be successfully prosecuted, whether through the ICC or a specialized environmental court. But because ecocide is a global problem that affects many different regions and transcends national boundaries, achieving this goal will require the cooperation of all major world powers, including the US, China, and the EU. China aims to be a leader in climate action, as evidenced by its environmental policies, which are designed to influence international norms and practices (Hurri, 2023). According to Hurri (2023), China is aiming to shape international climate policies and strengthen its position in international climate governance as a part of its broader efforts to enhance its global influence. However, the model of 'ecological totalitarianism', defined by Clement as a state-led system where environmental policies become a tool of authoritarian governance, limiting civil liberties while achieving environmental goals, China presents, raises questions about how to balance personal freedoms with environmental sustainability (Clement, 2021).

It is also important to remember that China and the US do not recognize the ICC and are not parties to the Rome Statute, which limits

the Court's ability to prosecute cases of ecocide. China's preference for national sovereignty over international jurisdiction and the US's concerns about potential political bias and sovereignty all play a role in their non-participation. For a global solution to be effective, these views must be included. Although not sufficient on its own, the inclusion of ecocide as a fifth international crime in the Rome Statute would be a significant step. For ecocide to be effectively addressed and prevented, there must be widespread international cooperation and commitment.

Conclusion

The essay has discussed the history and the evolving discourse on ecocide, highlighting its growing relevance. Although the origins of ecocide lie in environmental destruction in wartime, the growing awareness within the international community about climate change issues indicates the need to broaden the concept and apply it also during peacetime, as a crime that is so relevant that it should be prosecuted regardless of the context of war. However, although the Rome Statute and the Geneva Conventions recognize some environmental damage during warfare, the concept of ecocide remains underrepresented in international law. Therefore, many proposals were discussed on how to give ecocide more relevance in international law.

The debate also shows the need for an internationally recognized definition of ecocide and its wider application outside times of war. In addition to strengthening the legal framework, the international criminalization of ecocide would act as a deterrent to serious environmental damage. To promote environmental justice and protection on a global scale, ecocide must be recognized under international law and incorporated into any new or existing legal framework.

The effective management of ecocide requires the creation of thorough legal frameworks as well as specialized institutions to deal with complex

environmental problems. To ensure a sustainable and equitable future for all, the international community must take decisive action to fill the gaps in current legal systems and support strong mechanisms for the prosecution of environmental crimes.

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